

Supplementary Information for

Facile Synthesis of FAPbI₃ Nanorods

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Figure S1: XRD data of FAPbI₃ perovskite nanorods.

Figure S2: The stability of FAPbI₃ perovskite nanorods under UV illumination (365 nm, 12W) at ambient conditions: Change in the relative PL intensity of perovskite NC solutions vs UV illumination time.

Figure S3: The representative absorption and PL for FAPbI₃ and FAPbBr_xI_{3-x} perovskite nanorods.